

Stellar Mass Estimation of Kepler Exoplanet Host Stars Using Kepler’s Third Law with Monte Carlo Uncertainty Analysis

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Abstract

Host star masses for four confirmed exoplanets discovered by the Kepler mission (Kepler-10b, Kepler-186f, Kepler-62f, Kepler-452b) were calculated using orbital period T and semi-major axis a from the NASA Exoplanet Archive.

The Newtonian form of Kepler’s third law was applied:

$$M = \frac{4\pi^2 a^3}{GT^2}$$

where $G = 6.67430 \times 10^{-11} \text{ m}^3\text{kg}^{-1}\text{s}^{-2}$.

A Monte Carlo simulation (1000 samples) with $\pm 1\%$ assumed measurement uncertainty in both T and a yielded approximately 3.6% propagated uncertainty in the stellar mass, consistent with analytical error propagation from the a^3/T^2 dependence.

The host star of Kepler-452b was found to have a mass of $1.03 M_{\odot}$, very close to the solar value.

1 Introduction

The Kepler mission provided precise measurements of orbital periods and semi-major axes for thousands of exoplanets. For systems where the planetary mass is negligible compared to the host star, the third law of Kepler in its Newtonian form allows direct estimation of the stellar mass from orbital parameters alone.

This work presents calculations for four selected Kepler exoplanets and includes a Monte Carlo analysis of measurement uncertainty propagation.

2 Data and Method

Orbital parameters were taken from the NASA Exoplanet Archive:

Exoplanet	Orbital Period T (days)	Semi-major Axis a (AU)
Kepler-10b	0.8375	0.0168
Kepler-186f	129.9441	0.432
Kepler-62f	267.291	0.718
Kepler-452b	384.843	1.046

Table 1: Input orbital parameters.

Units were converted to SI (a in metres, T in seconds) and the stellar mass computed using the formula given in the abstract.

3 Results

The calculated stellar masses are presented below.

Figure 1: Estimated host star masses in solar units.

Figure 2: Estimated host star masses with Monte Carlo error bars ($\pm 1\%$ uncertainty in T and a , 1000 samples).

Figure 3: Artistic impression of Kepler-452b and its host star compared to Earth and the Sun (NASA concept).

The Monte Carlo simulation indicates an uncertainty of approximately 3.6% in the derived stellar mass for all systems, in agreement with the expected propagation from the a^3/T^2 functional form.

4 Conclusion

The host star of Kepler-452b is found to be very close to solar mass ($1.03 M_{\odot}$), reinforcing its status as one of the most Sun-like systems discovered by Kepler. The Monte Carlo approach demonstrates the sensitivity of stellar mass estimates to small measurement uncertainties in orbital parameters.